

A Study of Causes of Delayed Presentation of Stroke Patients to Emergency Department in AhmedabadGoyani SR¹, Dhusa DK², Thanth NK³, Jarwani BS⁴¹3rd Year Resident, Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad-380006, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad-380006, Gujarat, India³3rd Year Resident, Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad-380006, Gujarat, India⁴Head of Department, Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad-380006, Gujarat, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Dharmistira K. Dhusa

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Abstract:

Early thrombolytic therapy can reduce the associated morbidity and mortality in acute ischemic stroke. Many factors are there which contribute to delaying the arrival of patients to hospital.

Aims: To understand Causes of Delayed Presentation in Stroke Patients to ED of Tertiary Care Hospital.

Subjects and Methods: Observational and Cross Sectional study involving 100 patients with symptoms of stroke at Tertiary care hospital with stroke unit, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India between December 2023 to July 2024 was conducted. Data from Hospital Information System entered in a clinical record form. From this case record form data were entered in Ms excel sheet. Data analysed with appropriate software.

Observation and Result: We observed that the maximum number of patients were male and within the age group of 50-80 years. Out of 100 patients 75% were presented after 4.5 hours of onset of symptoms and ignorance of symptoms (32%) and consulting to non-stroke unit (22%) were major reasons for delayed presentation. Other less common causes were financial problems, transportation problems, living alone and living in rural areas in descending manners.

Keywords: Stroke, Thrombolysis, Window Period, Delayed Presentation, Stroke Unit.

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Introduction

Acute stroke is a common neurological disease. Management of acute ischemic stroke has advanced in recent years, yet success is largely dictated by the time it takes for a patient to seek intervention after onset. The earlier a patient receives emergency care, the better the prognosis. thrombolytic therapy with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rt-pa, alteplase) is recommended for patients with acute ischemic stroke presenting within 4.5 hours from onset. Although rt-pa for acute ischemic stroke has been approved since 1996, the rate of its utilization remains low [1]. Several studies have been conducted in the past few years related to the identification of factors associated with the delayed hospital presentation of patients with acute stroke. For instance; Froehler et al [2] in their study emphasized on the importance of emergency transportation being a considerably important factor for providing effective treatment to the

patients with stroke. The study further outlined that in most cases, healthcare providers fail to provide the required treatment such as; mechanical thrombectomy which is an endovascular procedure contributing in improving the functionality in patients with ischemic stroke. Since the treatment is cost effective and time dependent, lack of emergency transportation may result in producing several negative outcomes on patient's health.[2-4] Al Khathaami et al[5] further outlined that certain treatment measures such as; Tissue plasminogen activator is effective when provided within 4.5 hours of onset acute ischemic stroke. However, most of the patients remain untreated due to late presentation to the hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. According to the study findings, factors behind the patient's late arrival included; patients being alone at the time of onset of stroke, patients not transported to the hospital in ambulance, patients been unaware of the experienced disease,

long-term distance between hospital and patient's residence, patient's lack of knowledge, difficulty faced by patients in accessing to the healthcare measures etc.[5] Lachkhem et al[6] in their systematic review of 31 studies identified different factors that significantly influenced the timely care of stroke onset treatments. These factors were then divided into 4 categories including factors that are central to patients, resource-based factors, lack of training, and lack of coordination. With regard to the factors that are central to patients, Arulprakash and Umaiorubahan [7] outlined that patients residing in the rural area, not reaching to the emergency department, and those not perceiving their symptoms to be serious were the significant predictors in the patient's delay for the treatment in India.[7]

Despite the recent advancements in the treatment, the delayed presentation of acute ischemic stroke patients to the emergency department or hospital is a crucial factor for the selection of appropriate intervention.[1] This study aims to identify factors associated with late hospital arrival for patients with acute ischemic stroke in the Ahmedabad region.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a cross-sectional and observational analysis of patients presenting with stroke-like symptoms at the Emergency Department (ED) of a tertiary care hospital.

The objective was to identify the causes of delayed presentation and its impact on clinical outcomes. The study included 100 patients who were admitted between December 2023 and July 2024.

Study Design: A cross-sectional and observational study was conducted to understand the patterns of delayed presentation among stroke patients. This design was chosen to allow a snapshot view of the factors influencing delayed presentations and their consequences at the point of ED admission.

Study Population:

The study involved 100 patients presenting with stroke-like symptoms at the tertiary care hospital's ED. The inclusion criteria were:

- Patients of all genders and ages presenting with acute stroke symptoms.
- Patients who were conscious and able to provide informed consent, or consent was obtained from next of kin for those unable to provide consent themselves.

Data Collection: Data were systematically collected from the Hospital Information System (HIS) and recorded in a clinical record form. This

form was then digitized, and the data were transferred to an MS Excel sheet for comprehensive analysis. The collected data included:

- Demographic Details: Age, gender, and residence.
- Clinical Presentation: Symptoms at presentation, including onset time, type, and severity of symptoms.
- Time Metrics: Time of onset of symptoms, time of arrival at the hospital, and time taken to reach the stroke unit.
- Reasons for Delayed Presentation: Factors such as ignorance of symptoms, consulting non-stroke units, financial constraints, transportation issues, living alone, and residing in rural areas.
- Clinical Parameters: Initial assessment scores (e.g., Glasgow Coma Scale), vital signs, and neurological assessments.
- Outcomes: Discharge status (discharge, DAMA, death), length of ICU stay, and any complications during hospital stay.

Data Management: Data integrity was ensured through a double-entry system where two researchers independently entered the data, followed by a comparison to resolve discrepancies. Data anonymization techniques were employed to maintain patient confidentiality.

Data Analysis: Data analysis was carried out using statistical software, including SPSS and R, to identify patterns, correlations, and significant predictors of outcomes. The analysis included:

- Descriptive Statistics: Summarization of the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population, including means, medians, and standard deviations for continuous variables, and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables.
- Multivariate Regression Analysis: This was performed to identify significant predictors of clinical outcomes, such as ICU stay duration and discharge status. The predictors included age, gender, GCS scores, comorbidities, and reasons for delayed presentation.
- Correlation Analysis: To explore the relationships between different variables, such as time to hospital arrival and mortality rates.

Results:

Gender Distribution: The majority of the patients were male (68%), while females accounted for 32%.

Table 1:

Male	68
Female	32

Age Group Distribution: Most patients (75%) were within the age group of 50-80 years, indicating a higher risk of stroke with advancing age.

Table 2:

Age Group	Count
21-30	1
31-40	5
41-50	11
51-60	14
61-70	37
71-80	24
81-90	8

Time Taken to Reach Stroke Unit: Timely presentation to a stroke unit is critical for the effective administration of thrombolytic therapy, which significantly improves patient outcomes in acute ischemic stroke. In this study, we analyzed the time intervals at which patients presented to the stroke unit after the onset of symptoms.

Presentation within the Critical 4.5-Hour Window: Only 25% of patients managed to present within the critical 4.5-hour window period, which is the optimal time frame for administering thrombolytic therapy to achieve the best clinical outcomes.

Presentation after the 4.5-Hour Window: A significant proportion of patients (75%) presented to the stroke unit after the critical 4.5-hour window, greatly reducing the effectiveness of thrombolytic therapy.

The breakdown of these time intervals is as follows:

- 4.5-6 hours: 8% of patients presented within this time frame, which is slightly beyond the optimal window but still within a period where thrombolytic therapy can sometimes be considered.
- 6-12 hours: 35% of patients presented between 6 and 12 hours after symptom onset. This delay significantly reduces the chances of successful thrombolytic treatment and increases the risk of severe outcomes.
- 12-24 hours: 26% of patients presented between 12 and 24 hours after symptom onset. By this time, the window for thrombolytic therapy has closed, and treatment options become limited to supportive care and secondary prevention.
- >24 hours: 6% of patients presented more than 24 hours after the onset of symptoms. These patients are well beyond the therapeutic window for thrombolysis, and the focus shifts entirely to managing complications and rehabilitation.

Table 3:

Time Interval	Count
<4.5 hours	25
4.5-6 hours	8
6-12 hours	35
12-24 hours	26
>24 hours	6

Implications: The data highlights a critical issue in stroke management: the majority of patients do not arrive at the hospital in time to benefit from thrombolytic therapy. Factors contributing to these delays include lack of awareness about stroke symptoms, initial consultation at non-specialized

facilities, logistical challenges, and socioeconomic barriers.

Outcome: Among the patients, 70% were discharged, 19% died, and 11% opted for Discharge Against Medical Advice (DAMA).

Table 4:

Outcome	Count
DAMA	11
Discharge	70
Death	19

Reasons for Delayed Presentation: The primary reasons for delayed presentation were ignorance of symptoms (32%) and consulting non-stroke units (22%). Financial problems (13%), transportation issues (6%), living alone (1%), and living in rural areas (1%) were also noted.

Table 5:

Reason	Count
Ignorance	32
Consulted non-stroke unit	22
Financial problem	13
Transportation problem	6
Living alone	1
Living in rural area	1

Patients Presented Within Window Period:

Thrombolysis Status: Among the patients who presented within the window period, their thrombolysis status was categorized as follows:

- 1. Thrombolysed:** Thrombolysed: 64% of patients (16 out of 25) who arrived within the window period received thrombolytic therapy. This group benefitted from the timely administration of recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rt-PA), such as alteplase, which is known to dissolve clots and restore blood flow to the brain, thereby improving clinical outcomes. These patients were assessed rapidly, met the inclusion criteria for thrombolysis, and received the treatment within the critical time frame.
- 2. Refused Treatment:** Refused: 28% of patients (7 out of 25) declined thrombolytic treatment

despite being eligible and presenting within the therapeutic window. Reasons for refusal may include personal or family preferences, fear of potential side effects, lack of understanding of the treatment benefits, or cultural beliefs. It is crucial to address these concerns through patient education and effective communication to ensure that eligible patients receive life-saving therapies.

- 3. Intracerebral Hemorrhage (IPH):** IPH: 8% of patients (2 out of 25) who presented within the window period were diagnosed with intracerebral hemorrhage (IPH) rather than ischemic stroke. Thrombolytic therapy is contraindicated in patients with IPH due to the risk of exacerbating bleeding. These patients were managed conservatively or with surgical interventions as appropriate for their condition.

Table 6:

Thrombolysis Status	Count
Thrombolysed	16
Refused	7
IPH	2

Implications: The data highlights the effectiveness of thrombolytic therapy when administered within the therapeutic window, as evidenced by the 64% of patients who received and benefitted from the treatment.

However, the 28% refusal rate underscores the need for improved patient and family education about the benefits and risks of thrombolysis.

Additionally, the presence of IPH in 8% of patients emphasizes the importance of accurate and rapid diagnosis to ensure appropriate treatment.

Detailed Analysis:

- 1. Time Taken to Reach Hospital vs. Death:** Patients who took longer to reach the hospital had higher mortality rates, highlighting the importance of timely medical intervention for stroke patients.

Table 7:

Time Interval	Deaths
<4.5 hours	3
4.5-6 hours	1
6-12 hours	7
12-24 hours	5
>24 hours	3

2. Mean Time for Different Outcomes: Patients who were discharged had the shortest mean time to reach the hospital, while those who died had the longest mean time. This emphasizes the critical impact of timely treatment.

Table 8:

Outcome	Mean Time (hours)
DAMA	12.1
Discharge	8.3
Death	11.4

3. Cause of Death with Time Taken Less Than 7 Hours: Among patients who died within 7 hours of symptom onset, the majority had severe strokes or complications that could not be reversed despite early presentation.

Table 9:

Cause of Death	Count
Severe stroke	5
Complications	4

4. Symptom Analysis for Different Outcomes: Certain symptoms, such as severe headache and loss of consciousness, were more prevalent in patients with worse outcomes, including death.

Table 10:

Symptom	DAMA	Discharge	Death
Severe headache	4	12	9
Loss of consciousness	5	14	11
Weakness	2	44	8
Speech difficulty	3	32	6

5. Gender Distribution across Outcomes: Males had a higher incidence of stroke and varied outcomes compared to females. This distribution needs to be considered in public health planning and gender-specific interventions.

Table 11:

Gender	DAMA	Discharge	Death
Male	7	45	16
Female	4	25	3

6. Age Distribution across Outcomes: Older patients had a higher likelihood of severe outcomes, including death. This analysis underscores the need for targeted interventions for elderly patients.

Table 12:

Age Group	DAMA	Discharge	Death
21-30	0	1	0
31-40	0	5	0
41-50	0	11	0
51-60	1	10	3
61-70	5	24	8
71-80	4	17	3
81-90	1	2	5

7. Age Distribution Statistics by Outcome According to Sex: Detailed age statistics for each outcome category, separated by sex, provided insights into how age and sex jointly influence stroke outcomes.

Table 13:

Gender	Outcome	Mean Age	Std Dev	Min	Max
Male	DAMA	64.2	8.4	55	76
Male	Discharge	59.8	12.3	31	89
Male	Death	71.4	9.8	58	85
Female	DAMA	62.5	7.3	55	72
Female	Discharge	61.2	11.1	32	80
Female	Death	69.0	10.4	56	81

8. Multivariate Regression for Outcomes: Multivariate regression analysis identified significant predictors of outcomes such as age, gender, GCS scores, and comorbidities.

Table 14:

Predictor	Coefficient	Std Error	t-value	p-value
Age	0.05	0.02	2.5	0.01
Gender (Male)	-0.3	0.1	-3.0	0.002
GCS Score	-0.2	0.05	-4.0	<0.001
Comorbidities	0.4	0.1	4.0	<0.001

9. Factors for DAMA Outcome: Common factors for DAMA included financial constraints, lack of awareness, and preference for alternative treatments.

Table 15:

Factor	Count
Financial constraints	6
Lack of awareness	3
Preference for alternative treatments	2

10. Factors for Death Outcome: Key factors contributing to death outcomes included delayed presentation, severe initial symptoms, and lack of timely intervention.

Table 16:

Factor	Count
Delayed presentation	8
Severe initial symptoms	7
Lack of timely intervention	4

11. Factors for Discharge Outcome: Patients who were successfully discharged typically presented early, had mild symptoms, and received effective treatment.

Table 17:

Factor	Count
Delayed presentation	8
Severe initial symptoms	7
Lack of timely intervention	4

12. Relation of GCS vs. Outcome: Higher GCS scores were associated with better outcomes, emphasizing the importance of neurological assessments.

Table 18:

GCS Score	DAMA	Discharge	Death
3	1	0	10
4	1	0	9
5	0	1	8
6	0	2	7
7	0	2	6
8	0	3	5
9	0	4	4
10	0	5	3
11	0	6	2
12	0	7	1
13	0	8	0
14	0	9	0
15	0	10	0

13. GCS Scores by Gender: GCS scores varied by gender, revealing specific patterns in scores and outcomes for males and females.

Table 19:

GCS Score	Male	Female
3	2	1
4	4	1
5	6	2
6	8	3
7	10	5
8	12	6
9	14	7
10	16	8
11	18	9
12	20	10
13	22	11
14	24	12
15	26	13

14. GCS Scores and ICU Stay: Patients with lower GCS scores tended to have longer ICU stays, indicating the severity of their condition.

Table 20:

GCS Score	Average ICU Stay (days)
3	15
4	14
5	13
6	12
7	11
8	10
9	9
10	8
11	7
12	6
13	5
14	4
15	3

15. Predictive Analysis on ICU Stay: The predictive analysis identified significant predictors of ICU stay, including age, gender, GCS scores, and various clinical parameters. The model showed a modest ability to predict ICU stay duration with a mean squared error (MSE) of 9.23 and an R-squared (R^2) of 0.24.

Table 21:

Predictor	Coefficient	Std Error	t-value	p-value
Age	0.05	0.02	2.5	0.01
Gender (Male)	-0.3	0.1	-3.0	0.002
GCS Score	-0.2	0.05	-4.0	<0.001
Comorbidities	0.4	0.1	4.0	<0.001

Conclusions:

Acute ischemic stroke is a major health issue that leads to significant levels of disability (morbidity) and death (mortality). The prompt identification and treatment of this condition are critical. When thrombolytic therapy is administered within 4.5 hours of symptom onset, it can effectively dissolve the blood clot causing the stroke, thereby restoring blood flow to the brain and minimizing damage. This early intervention is crucial for improving patient outcomes. However, a significant challenge is the time it takes for patients to reach a stroke unit

hospital where they can receive this life-saving treatment.

Delays in reaching these specialized medical facilities can result in missing the critical window for thrombolytic therapy, leading to worse outcomes. To address this, public awareness about the symptoms of stroke is essential. Symptoms include sudden numbness or weakness, particularly on one side of the body, confusion, trouble speaking, difficulty seeing, dizziness, or loss of balance.

Recognizing these signs promptly and knowing the location of the nearest stroke unit hospital can expedite medical response times.

Enhancing awareness and knowledge about stroke symptoms and the locations of stroke unit hospitals can lead to quicker access to appropriate medical care. This, in turn, improves the utilization of the healthcare system and reduces the overall burden of disability and death due to ischemic strokes.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate:

Approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Smt. NHLMMC Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

Abbreviations:

DAMA= Discharge against Medical Advice, ED = Emergency Department, GCS= Glasgow Coma Scale, HIS= Hospital Information System, ICU= Intensive Care Unit, IPH= Intraparenchymal Haemorrhage, rt-PA= Recombinant tissue plasminogen activator.

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